

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Effect of Corporate Assets on Market Value of Oil and Gas Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of corporate assets on market value of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study specifically examined the effect of current assets, non-current assets and intangible assets on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study used ex-post facto research design. Data for the study were sourced from annual reports and accounts of sampled oil and gas firms. Data collected were analysed using multiple regression analysis. Result of the analysis shows that the study found out that current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Non-current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Intangible assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends that oil and gas firms in Nigeria should effectively utilize current assets in funding day-to-day operations and paying ongoing expenses as the study found out that current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Oil and gas firms in Nigeria should use non-current assets for long term investments as the study found out that non-current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Oil firms in Nigeria should invest more in intangible assets to further improve on their market value as the study found out that intangible asset has significant effect on the net share price of oil firms in Nigeria.

Keywords: Corporate Assets; Market Value; Oil and Gas Firms

Introduction

Assets other than goodwill that will contribute to future cash flows for both the cash-generating unit under evaluation and other cash-generating units are referred to as corporate assets (Pandey, 2007). The corporate firms have a variety of corporate assets, including tangible, intangible, and current assets. (Marsh, 2009). Non-current assets include things like buildings, land, furnishings, and so on. Investments in all of these sorts of assets can be used to create productive capacity and ensure long-term profit margins. The types of such assets don't vary very often. The primary goal of buying such assets is to increase production and sales. Assets play a big part in how profitable a company is.

There are many reasons why the assets are considered to be most important. Taiwo, (2012) noted that the non-current assets are about half of the total assets of the manufacturing firm and in a distribution firm. A greater return on investment can be obtained by having huge level of assets which are not current. However, Olowe, (2008) claims that there can be negative effect of profit of a firm on the current assets of the firm, while the deficiency of current assets may drop down the stock outs and the liquidity of a firm so that the liquidity of firms could not be disturbed.

Emekekwue (2014) defines investment as the art of planning expenditures whose return are expected to exceed one year. It involves a sacrifice of present consumption in exchange of future benefits. Since investment involves a sacrifice of present condition, there is an element of risk that future outcome may not be realized. The efficiency in the use of assets can be measured with assets turnover ratio. Pandey, (2010) opines that the assets turnover ratio measures the efficiency with which a firm is utilizing its investment in assets, such as land, building, plant and machinery, furniture and so on. It also indicates the adequacy of sale in relation to the investment in assets. It is a rough measure of the productivity of a company's assets with respect to generating sales. However, investors should look for consistency or increasing non-current assets turnover rates as positive statement of financial position investment qualities (Bragg, 2010).

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Statement of the Problem

Corporate asset factors are crucial in boosting the market value of businesses. Intangible assets, non-current assets, and current assets all have a role in how much a business is worth in the market. The market worth of such an organization is significantly impacted by an organization's capacity to convert its assets into cash within a year of the date of the statement of financial status. This is based on the idea that the availability of cash, which is frequently recovered from current assets, determines the range of business activities that take place within organizations.

Financial constraints have been a major factor affecting corporate firms' performance in developing countries especially Nigeria. The basis for the determination of optimal corporate asset in Nigeria is the widening and deepening of various financial markets. Mainly, the corporate sector is characterized by a large number of firms operating in a largely deregulated and increasingly competitive environment. Years back, financial liberalization has changed the operating environment of firms, by giving more flexibility to the Nigerian financial managers in choosing their firms' assets investments. Such investments depict the extent of cash-holding of the firm involved. This invariably has direct impact on share price which measures the **market value** of firms thereby necessitating the essence of the study on the effect of corporate assets on **market value** of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to appraise the effect of corporate assets on market value of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Other specific objectives are to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of current assets on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
- ii. Examine the effect of non-current assets on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
- iii. Investigate the effect of intangible assets on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions will address the stated specific objectives:

- i. To what extent do current assets affect share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effect of non-current asset on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria?
- iii. To what extent do intangible assets affect share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria?

Statement of Hypotheses

Following the above research questions, the study will consider the following null (H_0) hypotheses to guide the study. They include:

- I. Current assets do not have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firm in Nigeria
- II. Non-current asset does not have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
- III. Intangible assets do not have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Corporate Asset

An asset is an economic resource when it comes to financial accounting. An asset is anything, whether tangible or intangible, that can be owned, controlled, or used by a business to create value and is kept therein to generate profit (William, 2010). Assets, to put it simply, are the value of ownership that can be converted into money (although cash itself is also considered as an asset).

Intangible assets are non – physical resources and rights that have a value to the firm because they give the firm some kind of advantage in the market place (Tuller, 2008). Examples of intangible assets include goodwill, copyrights, trademarks, patents and computer programs, and financial assets, including such items as accounts receivable, bonds and stocks.

One of the most widely accepted accounting definitions of asset is the one used by the International Accounting Standards Board. The following is a quotation from the IFRS Framework: "An asset is a resource controlled by the enterprise as a result of past events and from which future economic benefits are expected to flow to the enterprise (Ray and Eric, 2009)." This means that:

- I. The probable present benefit involve a capacity, singly or in combination with other assets, in the case of profit oriented enterprises, to contribute directly or indirectly to future net cash flows, and, in the case of non-profit organizations, to provide services;
- II. The entity can control access to the benefit;
- III. The transaction or event giving rise to the entity's right to, or control of, the benefit has already occurred.

Current Assets

Any asset that can reasonably be expected to be sold, consumed, or exhausted during the regular course of business within the current fiscal year or operating cycle (whichever period is longer) is referred to as a current asset (Ozkan and Ozkan, 2012). Cash, cash equivalents, short-term investments (marketable securities), accounts receivable, inventory, supplies, and the portion of prepaid liabilities that will be paid within a year are examples of typical current assets. Prepaid liabilities are also frequently referred to as prepaid expenses. Simply put, current assets are assets held for a brief period of time. Such assets are anticipated to be realized in cash or consumed throughout the typical company operating cycle.

Assets are often divided into current assets and non-current assets on a statement of financial condition.

Total current assets divided by Total Current Liabilities yields the current ratio. It is widely used as a measure of a company's liquidity and short-term obligation-paying capacity.

The quick ratio, often known as the acid test, assesses a company's capacity to immediately retire its current liabilities using its near-cash or quick assets. Quick assets are those that, if needed, can be quickly converted into cash.

Non-Current Assets

Non-current assets are long-term investments made by the company whose full worth won't be realized during the accounting year (Adekunle, 2009). Investments in other businesses, intangible assets like goodwill, brand recognition, and intellectual property, and property, plant, and equipment are a few examples of non-current assets. Non-current assets are listed on the company's financial position statement.

Long-term assets are also known as non-current assets. Non-current assets are capitalized rather than expensed, which means that instead of allocating the entire cost to the accounting year in which the asset was purchased, the corporation allocates the cost of the asset across the number of years for which the asset will be used. The nature of asset will determine whether it is depleted, amortized, or both. All of these words, though, are only technical ways of recognizing expenses and reducing the value of noncurrent assets on the balance sheet.

Non-current assets are categorised in the financial statement under one of the following headings, according to Atuche (2009): investments, property, plant and equipment, intangible assets, or other assets. Only investments that are anticipated to not convert to unrestricted cash within the upcoming 12 months of the balance sheet date are classed as non-current. Land, structures, and equipment, including cars, are all considered to be property. Plant, equipment, and real estate are all examples of fixed assets. Last but not least, intangible assets are items that lack physical presence and cannot be touched. Intangible assets can be acquired, like a patent, but they can also result from the sale or purchase of company units.

The cash surrender value of life insurance is another non-current asset. Bond sinking funds established for debt repayment in the future are categorized as non-current assets. Additionally categorized here are some deferred income taxes, goodwill, trademarks, and unamortized bond issue costs.

If a future benefit is not expected to be obtained within a year, prepaid assets may be considered non-current assets. For instance, if rent is pre-paid for the next 24 months, the first 12 months are regarded as current assets because

the benefit will be utilized this year. The benefit will not be received until next year, so the remaining 12 months are not considered current.

Intangible Assets

Manufacturing companies depending on the structure of assets consist of two types of assets, non – current and current assets. The manufacturing companies use fixed assets to transfer the raw materials into finished goods. In 2012, the investments in non – current at large and medium-sized companies made 96.4% of the level of 2008 investments (Tuller, 2008). The growth rate of fixed capital in Sultanate of Oman is 10.5% for 2010 and the increase in fixed assets in the petro-chemical is 35% for 2012. Therefore, there is increasing importance of fixed assets to generate profit in the manufacturing companies. Sometimes, these companies accumulate a higher percentage of current assets, the second type of assets. In this case, there is an essential question concerning the role of non - current assets and current assets in generating the profit (Ikpefan, Owolabi, Agwu & Adetula, 2014). This question is very important in the industrial sector in Sultanate of Oman because most of the manufacturing companies have a destroyed assets structure.

Some of these companies have a higher percentage of fixed assets and a low percentage of current assets and vice versa; where the percentage of current assets is higher than the percentage of fixed assets. This means that the contribution of current assets is greater than the contribution of fixed assets to generate the net profit. This contribution is measured by assets turnover (current turnover and fixed turnover). In this regard, most of Omani manufacturing companies do not have intangible assets (Afza & Nazir, 2009).

Market Value

Market value is the price an asset would fetch in the marketplace (Korankye & Adarquah, 2013). Market value is also commonly used to refer to the market capitalization of a publicly-traded company, and is obtained by multiplying the number of its outstanding shares by the current share price. Olatunji and Adegbite (2014) state that market value is easiest to determine for exchange-traded instruments such as stocks and futures, since their market prices are widely disseminated and easily available, but is a little more challenging to ascertain for over-the-counter instruments like fixed income securities. However, the greatest difficulty in determining market value lies in estimating the value of illiquid assets like real estate and businesses, which may necessitate the use of real estate appraisers and business valuation experts respectively.

According to Gladys and Omagwa (2017), market value is the anticipated sum for which a property should trade on the valuation date between a willing buyer and a willing seller in a fair sale that follows a thorough marketing campaign in which all involved parties acted sensibly, responsibly, and without coercion. When compared to market price, which is the price at which transactions can take place, market value is the genuine underlying value. Inefficient markets or conditions of disequilibrium when prevailing market prices are not reflective of genuine underlying market value are where the concept is most frequently used. The market must be informationally efficient and rational expectations must prevail for market price to equal market value.

One of the accounting variables that measures market value is the earning per share. Taani (2012) states that share price (EPS) is the portion of a company's profit that is allocated to each outstanding share of common stock, serving as an indicator of the company's financial health. In other words, share price is the portion of a company's net income that would be earned per share if all the profits were paid out to its shareholders. Share price is used typically by analysts and traders to establish the financial strength of a company, and is often considered to be one of the most important variables in determining a stock's value.

Theoretical Framework

The effect of corporate assets on **market value** of oil and gas firms in Nigeria, has some number of theories underpinning it but the most relevant is trade – off theory.

Trade - Off Theory

The trade – Off Theory was propounded by Kraus and Litzenberger in 1986. The trade – off theory refers to the idea that a company chooses how much debt finance and how much equality finance to use by balancing the cost and

benefits. The classical version of the hypothesis goes back to Kraus and Lichtenberger who considered a balance between the deed-weight (Olowe, 2008).

According to the trade-off theory of capital structure, a company decides how much debt financing to use and how much equity financing to employ by weighing the costs and advantages. The traditional version of the hypothesis dates back to Kraus and Litzemberger, who explored a balance between the tax-saving advantages of debt and the dead-weight costs of bankruptcy. Agency fees are frequently added to the balance. This theory is designed to be a rival to the pecking order theory of capital structure (Bratland and Hornbrinck, 2013).

The theory's attempt to explain why firms often have a mix of debt and equity financing is one of its main goals. It claims that financing with debt has benefits, including tax benefits and costs associated with financial difficulty, including costs associated with bankruptcy and non-bankruptcy costs (such as workers departing, suppliers seeking unfavorable payment terms, bondholder/stockholder disputes, etc.).

When deciding how much debt and equity to use for financing, a firm that is maximizing its overall value will focus on this trade-off because the marginal benefit of further debt increases declines as debt increases while the marginal cost increases.

Modern Portfolio Theory

The Modern Portfolio Theory was postulated by Findlay & Hamilton in 1979. The theory approaches investing by examining the entire market and the whole economy. The theory is an alternative to the older method of analyzing each investment's individual merits. Investors look at each investment's individual merits, they are analyzing one investment without worrying about the way different investments will perform relative to each other. On the other hand, modern portfolio theory places a large emphasis on the correlation between investments. Markowitz in 1952 developed a basic portfolio model that demonstrated how risk could be reduced within a portfolio by combining assets whose returns demonstrate less than perfect positive correlation. The Markowitz theory exploited the low correlation between two assets and demonstrates that as long as the correlation between the two assets is low, the risk component of a portfolio would be less than the average of the risk of the individual assets (Edwin and Florence, 2016). Portfolio could be reduced by spreading the amount of funds available for investments into a variety of opportunities, each in a different risk class. Institutional investors have over the years achieved portfolio diversification using property and equity as their prime investments.

The study is anchored on the trade – off theory based on the premise that it emphasizes on the fact that firms use combination of debt and much equality finance in financing investments by balancing the cost and benefits.

Empirical Review

Current Asset and Share Price

Afza and Nazir (2009) made an attempt in order to investigate the traditional relationship between working capital management policies and a firms profitability for a sample of 304 non – financial firms listed on Karachi stock exchange (KSE) for the period 2004 – 2009 they study found significant difference among their working capital different industries moreover, regression result found a negative relationship between the profitability of firms and degree of negative relationship between the profitability of firms and degree of aggressiveness of working capital investment and financing policies.

Onipe, Umar, Abiola and Safiya (2015) studied Current Assets Management and Financial Performance: Evidence from Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The study was to examine the relationship between the Current Assets Management and Financial Performance: Evidence from Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. These varying parameters include the cash and bank balances, financial assets held for trading, derivative assets, loans and advances to banks and loans and advances to customers. An OLS model was formulated to compute the effect of CAM on financial performance. For model validation purpose, five-year data analysis was conducted. The study's sample utilizes data from 2010-2014 belonging to 15 deposit money banks operating in financial services sector as listed by the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). In empirical analyses, robust estimator was used. The results of the conducted analyses suggest a positive relation between the cash and bank balances, financial assets held for trading,

loans and advances to customers and Return on Asset. Another result of the study, on the other hand, suggests that derivative assets, loans and advances to banks have negative impact on return on asset.

Non-Current Asset and Share Price

Ubesie and Ogbonna, (2013) studied Evaluation of the Effect of Non-Current Assets on Return on Assets of Cement Manufacturing Industry in Nigeria. The objectives include; To assess the effect of investment in plant and machinery on the return on assets of cement manufacturing industry in Nigeria, to ascertain the effect of investment in land and building on the return on assets of cement manufacturing industry in Nigeria and to evaluate the effect of investment in motor vehicles on the return on assets of cement manufacturing industry in Nigeria. The period covered 2004-2013. The independent variables are Land and Buildings, Plant and Machinery, Motor Vehicles, Furniture and Fittings, while the dependent variable is Return on Asset. Annual accounts and reports were used for analysis and multiple regressions were used to validate the hypotheses. The findings show that there is effect of non-current assets on return on asset but is not significant in Nigeria. It also showed that the independent variable Plant and Machinery contributed more to Return on Asset but not significant. The recommendations included that there should be more investment in non-current asset especially plant and machinery in order to increase the return on asset of cement manufacturing industry in Nigeria. It is also recommended that firms in Nigeria should invest keenly in motor vehicles to ease the problem inherent in distribution of cement product in Nigeria.

Airat and Ekaterina (2016) studied evaluation of the effect of non-current fixed assets on profitability and asset management efficiency. The objective of the study was to investigate the problem, which stems from non-current fixed assets affecting profitability and asset management efficiency and to identify the impact of estimates and valuation in accounting for non-current fixed assets through several objectives, for example, explanation of the impairment tests of tangible and intangible assets under IFRS. The study used unit root test and ordinary least square. The study found out that the differences in the measurement of accounting figures under IFRS and EAS may directly affect the numerator of ratio calculations, their denominator, or both. In cases where the difference in measurement affects only the numerator or only the denominator, the effect of the changes is straightforward, easy to identify and to interpret. Identification and interpretation are less obvious in cases of numerous diverging effects on ratios.

Intangible Asset and Share Price

Gamayuni (2015) tested empirically the relationship between intangible assets, financial policies, and financial performance on the firm value at going-public company in Indonesia. Path analysis was used to ascertain the relationship between intangible assets, financial policies, financial performance, and firm value at going-public company in Indonesia in the year 2007 to 2009. This study also provides empirical evidence that Intangible assets, financial policies, financial performance have significant influence to the firm value simultaneously. Intangible assets have no significant influence to financial policies, but has positive and significant influenced to financial performance (ROA) and firm value. Debt policies and financial performance (ROA) influenced firm value positive and significant. Financial statements limitation in measuring and disclosing intangible assets is the cause of significant difference between book value equity and market value equity. Measurement and disclosure of intangible assets (intellectual capital) precisely and accurately is very important, because intangible assets have a positive and significant effect on the firm value.

Akinbola (2012) study found that lease option had positively affected the profit of the small and medium scale enterprises as did a similar examination by Salam, (2013) in Bangladesh on the performance of Medium enterprises SMEs. Malm, and Rosland, (2013), investigated the Bond-to-Total Debt Ratio on Firms' Performance and found an insignificant relationship between the bond-to-total debt ratio and firm performance. Several researchers have tested the effects of profitability on firm leverage.

Mary, John and Laurie (2010) examined the effect of inventory on firms' profitability before and after two catastrophic supply chain disruptions of the September 11, 2001 terrorist attacks and Hurricane Katrina, with the objective of determining whether there is evidence that inventory has been used as a means of developing supply chain resiliency and the stability of any such relationship. Using separate three-year periods (2001 – 2003) surrounding the disruptions, they applied univariate analysis to examine the macro-level effects on firms' profitability, selected growth measures, and inventory levels across manufacturers, wholesalers, and retailers. Utilizing balance sheet and income statement data, regression models were applied to isolate the effect of inventory

on profitability and also to test whether a change in the relationship between inventory and firms' profitability can be detected. The findings indicate the effect of inventory on firms' profitability and shows a significant decline for manufacturing in the post - September 11 period with no significant change in the post Katrina period.

Abdulrasheed, Khadijat, Sulu and Olanrewaju (2011) assessed inventory management in selected small businesses in Kwara State, Nigeria from 2000 to 2010. Using a regression model to explain the effect of inventory value on performance proxy by profit over a period of ten years, the study revealed that a Naira change in stock would cause almost a Naira (92 Kobo) change in profitability of selected businesses. This result indicated a strong positive relationship between inventory and profitability of small businesses in Kwara State of Nigeria. They thus concluded that small businesses are likely to generate higher profit if an effective inventory management is put in place.

Methodology

Research Design

Research design is the structure and strategy for investigating the relationship between the variables of the study. The study used *ex-post facto* research design. According to Kerlinger and Rint (2006) in the context of social science research an *ex-post facto* investigation seeks to reveal possible relationships by observing an existing condition or state of affairs and searching back in time for plausible contributing factors.

Sources of Data

The source of data was secondary. The main source of data included the financial statements of the selected companies from the oil and gas industry in Nigeria.

Population of Study

The population of this study consists of all companies under the oil and gas industry of Nigeria that are listed in Nigeria stock market. They are eleven (11) oil companies in Nigeria.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size of this study was consisting of three selected firms in the oil and gas industry in Nigeria. The sample size was ascertained using a scientific method. They are Oando Nigeria Plc, Conoil Plc and Capital Oil Plc. These three firms were selected based on the fact that the data for the three firms were all available for the duration of years under study.

Model Specification

A multiple regression model was used to test the effect of corporate asset variables (independent variables) on market value (dependent variable).

Thus, the model is represented as;

$$SP = F (CA, NCA, IA) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:

- SP = Share price (it is used as a proxy for market value)
- CA = Current Asset (it is used as a proxy for corporate asset)
- NCA = NON-Current Asset (it is used as a proxy for corporate asset)
- IA = Intangible Asset (it is used as a proxy for corporate asset)

In a linear regression form, it will become:

$$SP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CA + \beta_2 NCA + \beta_3 IA + \mu \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

- β_0 = Constant Term
- β_1 = Coefficient of CA
- β_2 = Coefficient of NCA
- β_3 = Coefficient of IA
- μ = Error Term

Analytical Procedure

In order to achieve the objective of this study, the research adopted panel least square regression model. The work used descriptive statistics and unit root test with the help of E-View econometric package to analyze the data.

Decision Rule

Reject null (H_0) if the t-statistics is greater than 2.0 and the probability value is less than 0.05 (5%), otherwise accept null

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data Presentation

Data for the study, sourced from the annual report of the selected companies were presented, tested and analyzed. The data collected were organized and used for testing the hypotheses. From the analysis and results generated, deductions and logical conclusions were obtained.

The abbreviations used to signify the variables of study in all the tables are shown in the appendix.

Table 1: Pooled data of Oando Nigeria Plc, Conoil and Capital Oil

	NCA (₦)	CA (₦)	IA (₦)	SP (₦)
OANDO – 10	51691060	22017398	38241819	67.00
OANDO – 11	80860880	33374063	44217469	67.00
OANDO – 12	99541189	30565935	69018654	67.00
OANDO – 13	103736359	39624211	69069118	69.00
OANDO – 14	117927934	40624211	66071011	80.00
OANDO – 15	141671195	46087535	83614617	83.00
OANDO – 16	191863726	42089123	78138749	82.00
OANDO – 17	290573480	57212923	93218236	88.00
OANDO – 18	279794899	62248599	88503824	88.00
OANDO – 19	292015886	66291215	99509663	93.00
CONOIL – 10	89218547	7445927	37643630	75.00
CONOIL – 11	119620518	11104221	44134119	78.33
CONOIL – 12	145928727	29326928	67488036	78.91
CONOIL – 13	189422248	34658110	90160569	80.00
CONOIL – 14	198636459	38098644	88252860	86.99
CONOIL – 15	233951908	37513632	92682555	86.00
CONOIL – 16	270439885	40185309	101956731	86.12
CONOIL – 17	261236649	51374123	99570920	99.00
CONOIL – 18	289800392	49302589	105373016	118.22
CONOIL – 19	295909333	55725488	117346602	118.52
CAPITAL OIL – 10	168262589	13100002	49359341	58.91
CAPITAL OIL – 11	182385333	17128365	57120003	60.00
CAPITAL OIL – 12	170147228	26225248	62107682	63.51
CAPITAL OIL – 13	198200839	21287123	76789377	69.00
CAPITAL OIL – 14	219204325	30326524	80150360	69.00
CAPITAL OIL – 15	238235879	35305479	80252704	69.00
CAPITAL OIL – 16	241305631	37531441	89156197	74.80
CAPITAL OIL – 17	253354286	41577452	103370938	75.00
CAPITAL OIL – 18	260350133	40677101	99128629	88.33
CAPITAL OIL – 19	269530410	44252177	122268629	88.01

Source: Financial Statement of the selected companies

Data Analysis

Data analysis depicts how the data collected for each of the companies are analyzed with diverse analytical tools.

Descriptive Analysis

Table 2: Description of the Characteristics of the Variables under Study for the pooled data of Oando Nigeria Plc, Conoil and Capital Oil

	LNCA	LCA	LIA	LSP
Skewness	-1.000589	-1.277835	-0.789867	0.511028
Kurtosis	3.268395	4.332848	2.700950	3.149222
Jarque-Bera	5.095942	10.38491	3.231237	1.333580
Probability	0.078240	0.005558	0.198768	0.513354
Observations	30	30	30	30

Source: Author's Computation from Eviews 9.0

Table 2 contains the description of the variables using normality test which comprises of Skewness, Kurtosis and Jarque – Bera Statistics. The table showed that the logs of non current assets, current assets and intangible assets were negatively skewed while the log of share price is positively skewed. It was also shown that the logs of non current assets, current assets and share price are leptokurtic as their kurtosis values are greater than three (3) while the log of intangible asset is less than three (3) and therefore, it is platykurtic.

The table also showed that the logs of non – current assets, intangible assets and share price are not normally distributed as their probability values are greater than 0.05 while the log of non – current assets is normally distributed as its probability value is less than 0.05.

Regression Analysis

Table 3: Regression Analysis Table

Dependent Variable: LSP
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 04/04/22 Time: 17:06
 Sample: 2010 2019
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 3
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 30

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNCA	0.229817	0.054814	4.192664	0.0004
LCA	0.429247	0.058467	7.341671	0.0000
LIA	0.507671	0.064116	7.918028	0.0000
R-squared	0.837159	Mean dependent var		4.370171
Adjusted R-squared	0.795467	S.D. dependent var		0.171467
S.E. of regression	0.133319	Akaike info criterion		-1.097511
Sum squared resid	0.479894	Schwarz criterion		-0.957392
Log likelihood	19.46267	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-1.052686
Durbin-Watson stat	0.025001			

Source: Researcher's Computation from E-views 9.0

Table 3 above shows that the R^2 is 0.837159 which is about 84%. The R^2 is used to explain the goodness of fit. Therefore, since it is about 84%, it implies that about 84% change in the dependent variable being log of share price is explained by the independent variables and the higher the R^2 the better fit the independent variables. Since the F – statistics is 19.46267 which is greater than 2.0 and the probability value is 0.025001 is <0.05. This shows that the model is significant and has a high goodness of fit.

Test of Hypotheses

The test of hypothesis was carried out as follows:

Step 1: Re-statement of the hypothesis in the null and alternate forms
Step 2: Statement of decision criteria
Step 3: Presentation of test result
Step 4: Decision

Test of Hypothesis one

Step 1: Restatement of the hypothesis.

Current assets do not have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Step 2: Statement of Decision Criteria

Reject H_0 if the t-statistics is >2.0 and the probability of the t-statistics is <0.05 .

Step 3: Presentation of test result

Step 4: Decision

Given the decision criteria to reject H_0 if the t-statistics is >2.0 and the probability of the t-statistics is <0.05 . Table 3 shows the t-statistics of log of current assets as $7.341671 >2.0$ with a probability of the t-statistics of $0.0000 <0.05$. We reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Step 1: Restatement of the hypothesis.

Non-current asset do not have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Step 2: Statement of Decision Criteria

Reject H_0 if the t-statistics is >2.0 and the probability of the t-statistics is <0.05 .

Step 3: Presentation of test result

Step 4: Decision

Given the decision criteria to reject H_0 if the t-statistics is >2.0 and the probability of the t-statistics is <0.05 . Table 3 shows the t-statistics of log of non – current assets as $4.192664 >2.0$ with a probability of the t-statistics of $0.0004 <0.05$. We reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that non-current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Step 1: Restatement of the hypothesis.

Intangible assets do not have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Step 2: Statement of Decision Criteria

Reject H_0 if the t-statistics is >2.0 and the probability of the t-statistics is <0.05 .

Step 3: Presentation of test result

Step 4: Decision

Given the decision criteria to reject H_0 if the t-statistics is >2.0 and the probability of the t-statistics is <0.05 . Table 3 shows the t-statistics of LTA as $7.918028 >2.0$ with a probability of the t-statistics of $0.0000 <0.05$. We reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that intangible assets do not have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The following results were generated from the analysis of study;

Discussion for Hypothesis One

Current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria due to the fact that the t-statistics of log of current assets being 7.341671 was greater than 2.0 while the probability value being 0.0000 was less than 0.05 . This discovery is in agreement with the finding of Abata (2014) who studied the impact of asset quality on performance of six largest banks quoted in Nigeria stock exchange. The author found out that a statistical relationship exists between asset quality and bank performance.

Discussion for Hypothesis Two

The study discovered that non-current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria based on the premise that the t-statistics of log of non – current assets which was 4.192664 was greater than 2.0 while the probability value being 0.0004 was less than 0.05 . This assertion is in agreement with the findings of Airat and Ekaterina (2016). They studied evaluation of the effect of non-current fixed assets on profitability and asset management efficiency and found out that the differences in the measurement of accounting figures under

IFRS and EAS may directly affect the numerator of ratio calculations, their denominator, or both. In cases where the difference in measurement affects only the numerator or only the denominator, the effect of the changes is straightforward, easy to identify and to interpret. Identification and interpretation are less obvious in cases of numerous diverging effects on ratios. It also agreed with the finding of Athar, (2012) who studied the relationship between Non-current Assets and Firms Profitability. The author found out that there is an association between Non-Current Asset and Firms Profitability indicating hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of Hypothesis Three

The study discovered that intangible assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria due to the fact that the t-statistics of intangible assets which was 7.918028 was greater than 2.0 while the probability value being 0.0000 was less than 0.05. This discovery is in agreement with the findings of Gladys and Omagwa (2017) who studied Asset Structure and Financial Performance: A Case of Firms Quoted under Commercial and Services Sector at the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Kenya. The authors found out that asset structure had a significant statistical effect on the financial performance. This assertion was also in agreement with the statement of Gamayuni (2015) tested empirically the relationship between intangible assets, financial policies, and financial performance on the firm value at going-public company in Indonesia. The author found out that intangible assets have no significant influence to financial policies, but has positive and significant influence to financial performance (ROA) and firm value.

Summary of Findings

The summary of findings for this study includes the following:

1. The study found out that current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
2. Non-current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
3. Intangible assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study showed that the logs of non – current assets, current assets and intangible assets are integrated of order zero while the log of share price is integrated of order one. The study also concluded that current assets, non – current assets and intangible assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Recommendation

1. It is recommended that oil and gas firms in Nigeria should effectively utilize current assets in funding day-to-day operations and paying ongoing expenses as the study found out that current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
2. Oil and gas firms in Nigeria should use non-current assets for long term investments as the study found out that non-current assets have positive and significant effect on share price of oil and gas firms in Nigeria.
3. Oil firms in Nigeria should invest more in intangible assets to further improve on their market value as the study found out that intangible asset has significant effect on the net share price of oil firms in Nigeria.

References

- Abat, M.A (2014). Impact of asset quality on performance of six largest banks quoted in Nigeria stock exchange. *Journal of Business and Finance*, 14(6)50-62
- Abdulrasheed, A., Khadijat, A. Y., Sulu, I. and Olanrewaju, A. A. (2011). Inventory management in small business finance: Empirical Evidence from Kwara State, Nigeria. *British Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 2(1), 49 – 57.
- Adekunle, P. (2009). Determinants of capital structure: empirical evidence from the Czech Republic. *Czech Journal of Economics and Finance*, 54, (7), 2-21.
- Afza, T. and Nazir, K. (2009). Working capital approaches and firm's returns. *Nigerian Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*. 11(1), 33 – 43.
- Afza, T., & Nazir, M. S. (2009). Working capital requirements and the determining factors in Pakistan. *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*. 6(3), 112-117.
- Airat M. I. and Ekaterina, Y. (2016). Evaluation of the Effect of non-current fixed assets on profitability and asset management efficiency, *International Journal of Environmental & Science Education*, 11 (15), 7745-7753.
- Akinbola, O.S. (2013). Working capital management and financing decision: synergetic effect on corporate profitability. *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 218 – 221.

- Ani, W. U., Okwo, I. M. and Ugwunta, D. O. (2010). Effects of working capital management on profitability: Evidence from the top five beer brewery firms in the world, *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 2(8), 66 – 82.
- Athar, I. (2012). Relationship between non-current assets & firms profitability, *Munich Personal RePEc Archive*, 12 (9), 19 – 22.
- Atuche, J.C. (2009). *Impact of Effective Management of Credit Sales on Profitability and Liquidity of Food and Beverage Industries in Nigeria*. An Unpublished B.Sc Project, Department of Accountancy, Faculty of Business Administration, Imo State University, Owerri.
- Bragg, J. W. (2014). Does organizational growth contribute to profitability? Evidence from Malaysian public listed companies. *International Journal of Business and Society*, 10(2)14-16
- Bratland, E., & Hornbrinck, J. (2013). An empirical study of the relationship between working capital policies and stock performance in Sweden, *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 4(1), 76 – 88.
- Emekewue, P. (2014). *Corporate Financial Management*. 6th Edition. Kinshasa: African Bureau of Educational Sciences.
- Gamayuni, R.R. (2015). The effect of Intangible Asset, Financial Performance and Financial Policies on the Firm Value. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 4(1), 76 – 88.
- Gladys, M., Omagwa j. (2017) Asset structure and financial performance: A case of firms quoted under commercial and services sector at the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Kenya. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8 (4), 27 – 42.
- Habib, A., Syed, Z. A. and Iqbal, M. (2012). Impact of investor sentiment on mean-variance tradeoff in Pakistan, *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 2 (7), 99 – 104.
- Harris, A. (2005). Working capital management: difficult, but rewarding, *Financial Executive*, 21 (4), 52 – 53.
- Hasan, A. K., Halil, E. A., Arzu, O. C., and Salih, D. (2011). The Relationship between Working Capital Management and Profitability: Evidence from an Emerging Market, *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 62(19), 61 – 67.
- Hassan, M. A., Liaqat, A., Ch. Abdul, R. and Muhammad, A. (2011). Impact of working capital management on profitability and market valuation of Pakistani Firms, *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 22(33), 49 – 54.
- Ikpefan, O.A., & Owolabi, F. (2014). Working capital management and profitability of the manufacturing sector: An Empirical Investigation of Nestle Nigeria PLC and Cadbury Nigeria Plc. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 14(4), 33 – 43.
- Kester, T (1999) Relationship between profitability and debt/asset ratio. *International Journal of Business and Finance*, 4(2) 56-60.
- Kester, G. (2010). An analysis of working capital management results across Industries. *American Journal of Business*. 20(2), 44 – 54.
- Kim, C. S., Mauer, D. C. and Sherman, A. E. (2013). Determinants of corporate liquidity - An analysis of cash holdings. *Journal of Business and Management*, 7 (2) 231-251
- Korankye, T., & Adarquah, R.S. (2013). Empirical analysis of working capital management and its impact on the profitability of listed manufacturing firms in Ghana. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(1).124-131.
- Lazaridis, I and Tryridis, D. (2012). The relationship between working capital management and profitability of listed company in the Athens stock exchange. *Journal of School of Business and Economics* 12(4) 226-231
- Makori, D. M., & Jagongo, A. (2013). Working capital management and firm profitability: Empirical evidence from manufacturing and construction firms listed on Nairobi securities exchange, Kenya. *International Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 1(1), 44 – 81.
- Marian, M. O., Ikpor, I. M. (2017). Impact of fixed asset investment on banks financial performance in Nigeria. *Funai Journal of Accounting, Business and Finance*, 1(8), 34 – 54.
- Martina, H. (2015), The relationship between assets and the capital structure of Croatian small and medium-sized enterprise. *Journal of School of Business and Management* 4(2) 126-231
- Mary, M. R., John, S. and Laurie, S. (2010). The Relationship between inventory management and firm profitability: sector consequences of catastrophic supply chain disruptions. *California Journal of Operations Management*, 8(2), 39 – 54.
- Melita, S. C., Maria, E. and Petros, L. (2010). The effect of working capital management on firm's profitability: empirical evidence from an emerging market. *Journal of Business & Economics Research*, 8 (12), 63 – 68.
- Muhammad, A., and Syed, I. H. (2011). Impact of working capital management on firms' performance: evidence from non-financial institutions of KSE-30 Index, *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 3 (5), 482 – 492.

- Mwangi, L.W., Makau, M.S., & Kosimbei, G. (2014). Effects of working capital management on performance of nonfinancial companies listed in NSE, Kenya. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(11), 195-205.
- Niresh, J.A. (2012). Working capital management & financial performance of manufacturing sector in Sri Lanka. *European Journal of Business Management*, 4(15), 12 – 19.
- Okwo, I. M., Ugwunta, D. O. and Agu, S. U. (2012). An examination of the factors that determine the profitability of Nigerian beer brewery firms. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 2(7), 741–750.
- Olatunji, T., Adegbite, T. (2014). Investment in fixed assets and firm profitability: empirical evidence from the Nigerian banking sector. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 1 (3), 78 – 82.
- Olowe, Rufus Ayodeji (2008). Stock Return, volatility and the global financial crisis in an emerging market: the Nigerian case. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 5 (4), 426-447
- Onipe A. Y., Umar M.K., Abiola A.S., and Safiya O. U. (2015) Current assets management and financial performance: evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13 (9), 23 – 44.
- Ozkan, A and Ozkan, N. (2012). Corporate Cash Holdings: An empirical investigation of Nigerian companies, *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 28(30), 12 – 17.
- Pandey, M. (2011). *Impact of working capital management on firms' Performance*. Enugu: New Generation Books.
- Salawu, S.E. (2007). Working capital management, firms' performance and market valuation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social and Human Sciences*, 6 (2), 119 – 219.
- Sania, U. (2012). Factors influencing individual investors behaviour in Karachi. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 2 (7), 33 – 47.
- Sveltana, D and Aaro H. (2012). Impact of investment fixed asset of selected companies in the European union member state. *Journal of Business and Management* 4 (2) 31-51
- Taani, K. (2012). Impact of working capital management policy and financial leverage on financial performance: Empirical evidence from Amman Stock Exchange – listed companies. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 1(8), 55 – 98.
- Taiwo, A. M. (2012). An empirical analysis of capital structure on firms' performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics*, 11 (6), 22 – 31.
- Ubesie, M. C. and Ogbonna, E. E. (2013). Evaluation of the effect of non-current assets on return on assets of cement manufacturing industry in Nigeria. *Journal of Theoretical & Applied Statistics*, 3 (2): 22-30.
- Van-Horne, A. (2014). Determining the impact of Dividends, invested capital and Retained Earnings on stock prices in Pakistan. *Journal of Policy and Development Studies*, 10(3), 1-19.
- Vida, M., Seyed, H. A. T. and Rezvan, M. (2011). The Relationship between working capital management and profitability of the companies (Case Study: Listed Companies on TSE). *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 76 (9), 159 – 164.